

The anhydride (IX): The anhydride (IX) was formed by refluxing II (0.5 g) with acetic anhydride (15 ml) or by stirring a mixture of III (0.5 g), acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (few drops) in ether as solvent at room temperature. The product crystallised from dioxane as yellowish silky needles, m. p. 270°-71°, yield 0.35 g. (Found : C, 64.4; H, 3.8. C₁₉H₁₂O₇ requires C, 64.77 and H, 3.4%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl) isocoumarin (III): The dicarboxyisocoumarin (II) (0.5 g) was heated in a metal bath at 258° for 3 to 4 min. (evolution of CO₂). The contents were boiled with water (5 ml) and the supernatant decanted off. Aq. NaHCO₃ extract of the residue on acidification gave a solid that crystallised from methanol as silky needles, m.p. 240-41°; yield 0.3 g. (Found C, 65.8; H, 4.3. C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires : C, 66.27; H, 4.3%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 242, 270, 310 nm (log ε : 4.53, 4.43, 4.21),

The methyl ester (IV): The methyl ester (IV) was prepared by refluxing III (1g) with methanol (60 ml) and conc. H₂SO₄ (1 ml) for 3 hr. The ester crystallised from ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. 163-64°, yield 0.8 g (Found: C, 66.7; H, 5.0. C₁₉H₁₆O₆ requires C, 67.05; H, 4.7 %).

2-Carboxy-4, 5-dimethoxybenzyl-12-carboxyphenyl ketone (VI): The isocoumarin (II or III) (1 g) was mixed with aq. NaOH (10 ml, 10%) and was left at room temperature for 10-15 min. The solution on acidification gave a solid that crystallised from ethyl acetate as cubes, m.p. 234°-35° (decomp.); yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 63.3; H, 4.7. C₁₈H₁₆O₇ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7%). The anhydride IX afforded VI on refluxing with aq. NaOH.

The ketone VI (1 g.) on keeping with H₂SO₄ (2.5 ml, 90%) and usual work up, gave isocoumarin III (0.8 g)

6, 7-Dimethoxy-3-phenylisocoumarin (V): The decarboxylation of II (0.5 g) was carried out exactly in the same procedure described before¹. The product crystallised from benzene as silky needles (0.3 g.) m.p. 165-66° (Found : C, 72.01; H, 5.0 C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires C, 72.45; H, 4.9%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 230, 270 and 320 nm (log ε : 4.31, 4.61, 4.27).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl)-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin (VII): To the methanolic solution of the ketone VI (0.5 g), NaBH₄ (0.5 g) was added in small portions at room temperature with shaking. Usual work up and crystallisations from ethanol yielded VII (0.4 g) as needles, m.p. 222°-23° (decomp.); (Found : C, 65.4; H, 4.7. C₁₈ H₁₆O₆ requires C, 65.87; H, 4.87%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 224, 255 nm (log ε : 4.64, 4.08).

6, 7-Dimethoxy-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin-3, 3'-spiropthalide (VIII): The ketone VI (1 g) was boiled with conc. HCl (30 ml) for 1 hr. On cooling the solid was filtered and washed with aq. NaHCO₃ and then with water. It crystallised from ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. 250°-52°; yield 0.8 g. (Found C, 66.5; H, 4.2; C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires C, 66.3; H, 4.3%), λ_{max}^{MeOH} 225, 270, 302 nm (log ε 4.59, 4.15, 3.94).

The above spiropthalide on heating with aq. NaOH (10%) on water bath and subsequent acidification with conc. HCl regenerated the ketone (VI).

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Formation of 1-Aroyl-2, 3-Phthaloylpyrrocolines

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It has already been reported¹ from this laboratory that the condensation product of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with isochroman-1, 4-dione in presence of hot pyridine was really 1-(0-carboxylbenzoyl)-2,3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ia) instead of 7,12-dihydro-5,7, 12-trioxo-5H-naphtho (2',3': 4,3) furo (3,2-c) isochromen (II) as suggested by Buu-Hoi *et al.*²

II

- Ia, R = R₁ = R₂ = H
 Ib, R = H, R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃
 Ic, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = OCH₃
 Id, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃
 Ie, R = CH₃, R₂ = H, R₁ = OCH₃

In the present communication it is intended to record some more examples of this type of condensation leading to pyrrocolines (I) to reinforce the previous conclusion. Thus, the condensation of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with 6,7-dimethoxyisochroman-1,4 dione³ in hot pyridine led to the pyrrocoline (Ib) which was converted to its ester (Id). The acid (Ib) when degraded with alkaline potassium permanganate gave α-picolinic acid detected by colour test with cyanogen bromide and β-naphthylamine⁴. The mass spectrum of the ester was

quite consistent with the structure (Id). The main peaks may be assigned as follows : m/e 469(M^+), 438($M^+ - OCH_3$), 410($M^+ - COOCH_3$), 274(III), 234.5 (M^{++}), 233 (IV), 191($410 - CO$) $^{++}$ and 190. The two acylium ion peaks at m/e 274 and 233 confirm the presence of acyclic ketone group.

Similar condensation of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with 7-methoxyisochroman-1, 4-dione⁵ afforded (Ic) which was esterified to give (Ie). The acid (Ic) on degradation with alkaline potassium permanganate furnished α -picolinic acid. It is therefore obvious that this type of condensation is general and results in the formation of compounds of the type (I). The mechanism of the condensation has been described in the previous communication.¹

Experimental

1-(2'-Carboxy-4', 5'-dimethoxybenzoyl)-2, 3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ib): A solution of 6,7-dimethoxyisochroman-1,4-dione (0.12 g.) and 2, 3-dichloronaphthoquinone (0.1 g.) in pyridine (2 ml.) was refluxed for 24 hours. The excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, residue taken up in water, and the mixture filtered. The dark red crude *pyrrocoline* afforded shining needles (50 mg.) from acetic acid, m. p. 265°. (Found : C, 68.3 ; H, 3.4 ; N, 3.0 : $C_{26}H_{17}O_7N$ requires : C, 68.6 ; H, 3.7 ; N, 3.1%). ν_{max} 1702 cm^{-1} (acid carbonyl), 1690 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl) and 1675 cm^{-1} (quinone carbonyl).

1-(2'-Carbomethoxy-4', 5'-dimethoxybenzoyl)-2, 3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Id): The above acid was treated with ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (1 g.) and left overnight. The excess of diazomethane was decomposed by adding a few drops of glacial acetic acid and the ether solution filtered to collect the *ester*. Crystallisation from acetic acid yielded shining red needles (20 mg.), m. p. 238°. (Found : C, 68.9 ; H, 3.8 ; N, 2.8 : $C_{27}H_{19}O_7N$ requires : C, 69.1 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 3.0%) ν_{max} 1722 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl), 1682 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl) and 1650 cm^{-1} (quinone carbonyl).

Oxidative degradation: The acid (Ib ; 0.1 g.) was refluxed with aqueous potassium permanganate (0.4 g. in 20 ml.) and 10% sodium hydroxide solution (4 ml.) for 6 hrs. and then cooled. Excess of potassium permanganate was destroyed by addition of a few drops of alcohol, the precipitated manganese dioxide filtered off and the colourless filtrate was made strongly alkaline and concentrated. The concentrated solution was made just acidic with concentrated hydrochloric acid, evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, and the

residue extracted with ethyl alcohol (5 ml.). A mixture of this solution (1 ml.), a crystal of cyanogen bromide and a little of β -naphthylamine was warmed gently for some time when an orange colour developed indicating the presence of α -picolinic acid.

1-(2'-Carboxy-4'-methoxybenzoyl)-2,3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ic): 7-methoxyisochroman-1, 4-dione (0.1 g.) and 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone (0.1 g.) were taken in pyridine (2 ml.) and the mixture refluxed for 24 hrs. The excess of pyridine was distilled off in vacuum, the deep red residue taken up in water and filtered. The *phthaloyl pyrrocoline* crystallised from acetic acid in bright red prisms (40 mg.), m. p. 263°. (Found : C, 70.2 ; H, 3.4 ; N, 3.0 : $C_{25}H_{15}O_6N$ requires : C, 70.6 ; H, 3.6 ; N, 3.3%).

1-(2'-Carbomethoxy-4'-methoxybenzoyl)-2, 3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ie): The above acid was esterified with diazomethane in the usual manner. Crystallisation from acetic acid afforded bright red needles of the *ester*, m. p. 202°. (Found : C, 71.0 ; H, 3.8 ; N, 3.0 : $C_{26}H_{17}O_6N$ requires : C, 71.1 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 3.2%). ν_{max} 1722 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl), 1695 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl) and 1670 cm^{-1} (quinone carbonyl).

Oxidative degradation: The above acid was degraded by aqueous potassium permanganate in presence of 10% sodium hydroxide, worked up in the same way as described in the previous case. The test of α -picolinic acid was done in a similar way.

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Inhibitive Effect of some Compounds Towards Corrosion of Copper in Potassium Persulphate Solution

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TURRENTINE¹ studied the dissolution of copper in an ammonical solution of persulphate. Scagliarini and Torelli² showed that copper acts as a catalytic agent in the oxidation of ammonia by persulphate. Ditz³ observed no formation of activated oxygen or